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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
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**11-Cooperation of Governmental Institutions
And Advocacy Associations Within the
Framework of The Fundamental Freedoms:
Conceptual Perspective. By Olena
Bondarchuk- Ladna and others. p. 228.**

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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
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**CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH – DENMARK
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(11)

**COOPERATION OF GOVERNMENTAL INSTITUTIONS
AND ADVOCACY ASSOCIATIONS WITHIN THE
FRAMEWORK OF THE FUNDAMENTAL FREEDOMS:
CONCEPTUAL PERSPECTIVE**

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ABSTRACT

The relevance of the study is due to the very legal nature of human rights organizations. It is human rights organizations which are entrusted with the function of monitoring the human rights situation in specific States, and this is the basis for

interaction between these subjects of international law. The purpose of the study is to provide a comprehensive examination of the selected human rights organizations and their role in ensuring the observance of human rights in specific States; the object of the study is public relations regarding the impact of human rights organizations on the observance of human rights in certain States at the appropriate level. The study used the methods of analysis, synthesis, statistical method and method of legal hermeneutics as special research methods. As a result of the work, the authors focused primarily on the theoretical understanding of the rule of law and its importance for the activities of human rights organizations. The paper also highlights the issue of the right to a fair trial in Ukraine as a fundamental right designed to ensure human rights. Attention is focused on the control function as a fundamental function of interaction between the State and human rights organizations in the protection of human rights. The author characterizes the activities of the United Nations (further – UN) in the field of human rights. The role and importance of such human rights organizations as Amnesty International, Human Rights Watch and the International Federation for Human Rights and their influence on states in ensuring human rights are also described. The publication provides a brief description of the World Human Rights Report 2024 prepared by Amnesty International, as well as the Human Rights Report 2024 with the participation of Human Rights Watch.

Keywords: *state, rule of law, right to a fair trial, control function, United Nations.*

1- INTRODUCTION

The relevance of studying the theoretical aspects of interaction between the State and human rights organizations in ensuring human rights is related to the fact that at the present stage of development of the rule of law in its legal sense, unfortunately, the problem of non-compliance with human rights often arises, which can negate the very existence of the rule of law and the rule of law as a guiding principle that has its legal basis in modern countries. It is the activities of human rights organizations that are aimed at influencing governments to ensure that the state of human rights is at the proper level. The main question was and still is whether the activities of human rights organizations can be called sufficiently effective in fulfilling their main function – the protection of human rights.

Also, in the framework of this work, it is worth focusing on the fact that the activities of human rights organizations in the framework of interaction with the states that are their members are aimed at establishing the rule of law. It is the realization of this principle that allows us to state that a state is a state governed by the rule of law. This aspect of the subject matter is reflected in this scientific publication.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

We propose to start this key element of the study with a review of the fundamental international legal acts in the field, which is related to the protection of human rights.

The first such normative document will be the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights consists of 30 articles and contains a general description of human rights¹. The next documents worth mentioning are the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966 and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of 1966. From the very name of the Covenants, one can already have a general idea of their content – the first is devoted to civil and political rights, and the second – to economic, social and cultural rights^{2, 3}. In the field, which is related to the protection of human rights, there is also such a legal document as the Convention against torture and other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment of 1984. One of the objectives of this Convention is to increase the effectiveness of the fight against torture and other inhuman, cruel or degrading treatment or punishment⁴. The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women of 1979 contains provisions on the equality of rights of women and men⁵. And finally, let's mention the Convention on the rights of the child of 1989, which enshrines the fundamental norms regarding the rights of children⁶.

Next, we will focus our attention on theoretical sources related to the topic of this paper. They can be divided into four groups: 1) those that relate to specific human rights; 2) those that highlight the relationship between artificial intelligence and human rights; 3) those that reflect the importance and role of treaties, which are related to human rights on the international level; 4) those that relate to international law, that regulates human rights.

An interesting work is Nehaluddin and Lilienthal⁷, who have prepared a critical review of international instruments to ensure as a human right the right to water. The scientific publication by Sekalala et al.⁸ on the decolonization of human rights. Sekalala et al.⁹ raised such an important research topic as laws about intellectual property leading

¹ Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948). https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_015#Text

² International Pact about civil and political rights (1966). https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_043#Text

³ International Pact on economic, social and cultural rights (1966). https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_042#Text

⁴ Convention against torture and other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment (1984). https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_085#Text

⁵ United Nations Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (1979). https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_207#Text

⁶ Convention on the rights of the child (1989). https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_021#Text

⁷ Nehaluddin, A., & Lilienthal, G. (2021). Right to water as a human right: A critical overview of international instruments. *Environmental Policy and Law*, 50(4-5), 299-308. <https://doi.org/10.3233/EPL-200232>

⁸ Sekalala, S., Forman, L., Hodgson, T., Mulumba, M., Namyalo-Ganafa, H., & Meier, B. M. (2021). Decolonising human rights: how intellectual property laws result in unequal access to the COVID-19 vaccine. *BMJ global health*, 6(7), e006169. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2021-006169>

⁹ Sekalala, S., Forman, L., Hodgson, T., Mulumba, M., Namyalo-Ganafa, H., & Meier, B. M. (2021). *Id.*

to the situation, that access to the COVID-19 vaccine is unequal. Kawwass et al.¹⁰ in their own scientific publication examined the right, that is related to health care through the prism of evolution. Lubis¹¹ is the author of a scientific article, in which a comparative analysis about the right to a fair trial, is characterized.

Lubin's¹² work on the right to data protection and privacy under law of human rights and humanitarian international law is also worthy of mentioning in our study. The work of Abimbola et al.¹³ is original, dealing with the women's rights in indigenous systems, which take place in Nigeria. It is also worth mentioning the scientific work of Cohen and Karim¹⁴, in which scholars raised the issue of rethinking gender inequality and political violence through the prism of equality for women in the context of war.

Gutterman¹⁵ devoted his own scientific publication to the right of health under law of human rights on the international level.

Jones¹⁶ discusses the responsibility of online platforms to respect human rights. Ventura et al.¹⁷ describe the role and importance of health mental care in the context of ethical issues and human rights. The topic of Newman et al.¹⁸ is unusual. It concerns a literature review on human rights of LGBT+ inclusion in Thailand.

¹⁰ Kawwass, J. F., Penzias, A. S., & Adashi, E. Y. (2021). Fertility – a human right worthy of mandated insurance coverage: the evolution, limitations, and future of access to care. *Fertility and Sterility*, 115(1), 29-42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fertnstert.2020.09.155>

¹¹ Lubis, A. F. (2023). The right to a fair trial: Comparative analysis of international human rights standards. *The Easta Journal Law and Human Rights*, 1(03), 116-126. <https://doi.org/10.58812/eslhr.v1i03.88>

¹² Lubin, A. (2022). The rights to privacy and data protection under international humanitarian law and human rights law. In *Research Handbook on Human Rights and Humanitarian Law* (pp. 462-491). Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781789900972.00035>

¹³ Abimbola, F. O., Ehiane, S. O., & Tandlich, R. (2023). Women's Rights in Nigeria's Indigenous Systems: An Analysis of Non-Discrimination and Equality under International Human Rights Law. *Social Sciences*, 12(7), 405. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci12070405>

¹⁴ Cohen, D. K., & Karim, S. M. (2022). Does more equality for women mean less war? Rethinking sex and gender inequality and political violence. *International organization*, 76(2), 414-444. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0020818321000333>

¹⁵ Gutterman, A. S. (2023). Right to health under international human rights law. *Older Persons' Rights to Physical and Mental Health*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4316428>

¹⁶ Jones, K. (2021). Protecting political discourse from online manipulation: The international human rights law framework. *European Human Rights Law Review*, 1, 68-79. https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/documents/issues/religion/cfi-ga76/submissions/2022-12-19/submission-freedom-thought-ga76-others-katejones-2_0.pdf

¹⁷ Ventura, C. A. A., Austin, W., Carrara, B. S., & de Brito, E. S. (2021). Nursing care in mental health: Human rights and ethical issues. *Nursing Ethics*, 28(4), 463-480. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0969733020952102>

¹⁸ Newman, P. A., Reid, L., Tepjan, S., & Akkakanjanasupar, P. (2021). LGBT+ inclusion and human rights in Thailand: a scoping review of the literature. *BMC public health*, 21, 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-11798-2>

The second group of theoretical sources concerns the relationship between artificial intelligence and human rights.

The work of Fukuda-Parr and Gibbons¹⁹ concerns the formation of a consensus on “ethical artificial intelligence”. Baldassarre et al.²⁰ prepared a systematic review of best practices in the field of human rights through the lens of responsible artificial intelligence.

The third group of theoretical sources reflects the importance and role of treaties, which are related to human rights on the international level.

Hoffman et al.²¹ argue that treaties on the international level have largely failed to achieve the desired effect, with the exception of international trade and financial law.

Simmons²² describes the impact of treaty ratification on human rights outcomes.

The last, fourth group relates to international human rights law. We also consider it necessary to mention the academic work of Contesse²³, which deals with the rules of consultation in human rights law on the international level. However, Contesse²⁴ notes that the attention of law enforcement officials has been almost entirely focused on jurisdiction in cases before the courts.

The next academic work we would like to mention is Benvenisti²⁵. It deals with the so-called “international law of occupation”.

Van Steenberghe²⁶ is the author of a scientific article on the impact of human rights on the regulation of armed conflicts. The legal nature of human rights is the subject of Nowak²⁷.

¹⁹ Fukuda-Parr, S., & Gibbons, E. (2021). Emerging consensus on ‘ethical AI’: Human rights critique of stakeholder guidelines. *Global Policy*, 12, 32-44. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1758-5899.12965>

²⁰ Baldassarre, M. T., Caivano, D., Nieto, B. F., Gigante, D., & Ragone, A. (2024). Fostering human rights in responsible AI: a systematic review for best practices in industry. *IEEE Transactions on Artificial Intelligence*, 6(2), 416-431. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAI.2024.3394389>

²¹ Hoffman, S. J., Baral, P., Rogers Van Katwyk, S., Sritharan, L., Hughsam, M., Randhawa, H., ... & Poirier, M. J. (2022). International treaties have mostly failed to produce their intended effects. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 119(32), e2122854119. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2122854119>

²² Simmons, B. A. (2023). Mobilizing for human rights: international law in domestic politics. In *Leading Works in International Law* (pp. 177-188). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003133407-11>

²³ Contesse, J. (2021). The Rule of Advice in International Human Rights Law. *American Journal of International Law*, 115(3), 367-408. <https://doi.org/10.1017/ajil.2021.22>

²⁴ Contesse, J. (2021). *Id.*

²⁵ Benvenisti, E. (2023). The international law of occupation. In *Leading Works in International Law* (pp. 22-36). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003133407-2>

²⁶ Van Steenberghe, R. (2022). The impacts of human rights law on the regulation of armed conflict: A coherency-based approach to dealing with both the “interpretation” and “application” processes. *International Review of the Red Cross*, 104(919), 1345-1396. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1816383122000133>

Tømte and Riyadi²⁸ explored the issues of local courts and human rights on the international level in Indonesia. Cerna²⁹ described the case of *Gambia v. Myanmar* in terms of provisional measures, which can change law of human rights on the international level.

The review of theoretical sources showed that there is currently no comprehensive scientific study of the interaction between human rights organizations and the state in ensuring human rights. The available doctrinal works relate either to individual human rights, or to the relationship between artificial intelligence and human rights, or to the role and significance of treaties, which establish human rights at the international level or law of the human rights on the international level. This state of affairs demonstrates the need for a study on the chosen topic.

The purpose of the study is to comprehensively examine the organizations, which activity is connected with protection of human rights and their role in ensuring the observance of human rights in specific states. To achieve this goal, the following objectives were set:

- to describe theoretical approaches to understanding the rule of law;
- to identify the problems of the rule of law in Ukraine;
- to describe the control function as an important aspect of interaction between the state and human rights organizations in the context of human rights observance;
- to focus on the activities of such human rights organizations as the United Nations, Amnesty International, Human Rights Watch and the International Federation for Human Rights. These tasks helped us to fully reveal the purpose of the work.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In conducting the study, the authors used both general scientific and special scientific research methods, which allowed them to comprehensively cover the topic of theoretical aspects of interaction between the state and human rights organizations in ensuring human rights. We used the method of analysis to consider the functions and importance of international human rights organizations, and to systematically outline the main provisions of legal acts concerning the activities of the latter. The method of

²⁷ Nowak, M. (2022). What are human rights?. In *The Routledge Companion to Music and Human Rights* (pp. 13-27). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003043478-3>

²⁸ Tømte, A., & Riyadi, E. (Eds.). (2024). *International Human Rights and Local Courts: Human Rights Interpretation in Indonesia*. Taylor & Francis. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003431350>

²⁹ Cerna, C. M. (2021). Provisional Measures: How International Human Rights Law is Changing International Law (Inspired by *Gambia v. Myanmar*). *Notre Dame Journal of International & Comparative Law*, 11(1). <https://scholarship.law.nd.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1130&context=ndjicl>

synthesis helped to summarize the results of the conducted study, given the results obtained during the research.

The special research methods used were the statistical method and the method of legal hermeneutics. The statistical method was used to display statistical data from a survey of lawyers on the observance of the principle of equality in the judicial process, as well as to consider the total number of cases under the jurisdiction of the European Court of Human Rights. The method of legal hermeneutics allowed us to describe the phenomenon of the rule of law, its characteristics, features and peculiarities.

4. RESULTS

Before highlighting the theoretical aspects of the interaction between the state and human rights organizations in the context of ensuring human rights, we should focus on such issues as the understanding of the rule of law and human rights organizations themselves. Here, the approach of Vovk³⁰ is noteworthy, which interprets the rule of law as a modern form of state power, which is embodied in the legal and administrative form of activity and organization of society and public authorities. According to Vovk³¹, human life and health, dignity and honor, inviolability, and other freedoms and rights are the value of such a state, and their provision is based on the rule of law through the interconnected activities of all branches of government. Thus, it is the ensuring and observance of human rights that constitutes a kind of “indicator” of whether we can call a state a state governed by the rule of law. In order for human rights to be ensured at the proper level, the state must have certain “mechanisms” for such ensuring. One of the classic mechanisms is the division of the branches of government into three branches: judicial, executive and legislative.

In our opinion, the possibility of a person's access to the fair trial right is not only a human right, which is fundamental, and a sign of the rule of law, but can also be viewed in terms of a mechanism designed to ensure the functioning of human rights. Why do we consider the right to a fair trial to be so important and mention it separately? Because it is through the courts that human rights violations are appealed in cases of non-compliance. Ukraine has a three-tiered system of courts: first instance, appeal, and cassation. It would seem that the possibility of appealing a court decision twice can protect a party to a court proceeding from an unfair court decision. At the same time, the so-called “corruption” elements in the judicial system are a well-known fact that jeopardizes the status of Ukraine as a country governed by the rule of law. Taking into account the numerous judicial reforms in Ukraine, we can state that Ukraine is on the way to becoming a state governed by the rule of law. The results of the survey among lawyers on the observance of the principle of equality in the judicial process in modern Ukraine are shown in Figure 1.

³⁰ Vovk, P. (2020). Rule of law: domestic scientific approaches to the content of the concept. *Methodology of the theory and practice of jurisprudence*, 1, 19-23. <https://doi.org/10.32837/yuv.v0i1.1531>

³¹ Vovk, P. (2020). *Id.*

The number of applications to the European Court of Human Rights is also a kind of “indicator” of the rule of law in a particular political regime. As of 2024, Ukraine ranks third in terms of the number of cases pending before the European Court of Human Rights (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Survey among lawyers without limitation of the area of practice in which they work on the observance of the principle of equality of parties in the judicial process in Ukraine, %

Source: developed on the basis of Aljeksjejeva³²

Figure 2. Number of cases filed with the European Court of Human Rights (top three anti-leader states)

Source: developed on the basis of³³

An important aspect of interaction between human rights organizations and the state is the control function. The special development of such a system in the human rights' field can be illustrated by the example of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966, which contains obligations for parties to submit reports on the status of implementation of the Covenant by such parties to the Human Rights Committee. The Committee prepares a report to the UN Economic and Social Council.

³² Aljeksjejeva, A. (2025). Systemic Violations of the Right to a Fair Trial in Ukraine: Analysis of IAC ISHR Surveys. <https://yur-gazeta.com/publications/practice/inshe/sistemni-porushennya-prava-na-spravedliviy-sud-v-ukrayini-analiz-opituvan-iac-ishr.html>

³³ Ukraine ranks third in terms of the number of cases pending before the ECHR (2024). <https://zmina.info/news/ukrayina-na-tretomu-misczi-za-kilkistyu-sprav-shho-perebuwayut-na-rozglyadi-u-yespl/>

Observation missions of the organizations are also sent to the field for monitoring purposes.

Before highlighting the main aspects of cooperation between human rights organizations and the state in the human rights' protection, authors consider it necessary to outline the periodization of the latter's development, which is set out in Table 1.

Table 1. Genesis and Periodization of International Human Rights Organizations

Periodization	Name of the organization	Examples of the main legal acts adopted during this period	General description of the activities of human rights organizations during this period
Initial stage (nineteenth century – early twentieth century)	American Civil Liberties Union; International Association for Human Rights; League of Nations	Universal Declaration of Human Rights	The first human rights organizations were established, focusing their activities against discrimination, violence and slavery
Formalization phase (1945 – 1970s)	UN; Amnesty International; Human Rights Watch	International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights	After the Second World War, there was a tendency to intensify the activities of human rights organizations, particularly in the United States and Europe
Globalization phase (1980s – 1990s)	International Federation of Human Rights organization "Secretariat"	Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women; Convention on the Rights of the Child	Internationally, the activities of human rights organizations are expanding and new ones are emerging
Modern stage (2000s – present)	Freedom House International; Justice Mission	Paris Declaration on Human Rights in the 21st Century	In the context of globalization, the activities of human rights organizations have intensified, the participation of citizens in human rights initiatives has increased, and new technologies have been integrated

Source: developed by the authors

In general, the influence of human rights organizations on the human rights situation has four aspects, which are schematically shown in Figure 3.

In the context of our work, it is worth mentioning, first of all, the UN as a universal (global) international organization, the fundamental purpose of which is to improve and maintain international security, improve state cooperation and ensure peace. Considering the institutional mechanism of the UN, it is worth noting that it is composed of institutions and agencies that are clearly regulated. The latter have inherent functional responsibilities aimed at protecting human rights. It was under the auspices of the UN that not only were declared, but also successfully implemented governing legal acts at the international level, which enshrined human rights standards on the international level. The universal institutional mechanism of the human rights protection system in the context of the UN is in continuous development and represents a dynamic component. The emergence of new institutions in this system illustrates this statement.

Figure 3. Influence of human rights organizations on the human rights situation

Source: developed on the basis of³⁴

Let us give the following example. The World Conference on Human Rights, which is part of the UN system, in 1993, created the post of the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights in order to strengthen the UN mechanism of the human rights. This Commissioner began his work in 1994. He is called upon to coordinate the activities of the entire human rights system in the UN, to improve and develop mechanisms aimed at human rights protecting, to take actions designed to ensure the effective and full application of the

³⁴ Human rights activism and the role of non-governmental organizations (2025). <https://www.coe.int/uk/web/compass/human-rights-activism-and-the-role-of-ngos>

normative system that establishes and protects international standards of human rights, and to investigate the most serious violations of human rights.

The next human rights organization that authors will consider in the context of our research is Amnesty International. Amnesty International is an international non-governmental organization whose main purpose is to promote all human rights, to conduct research and action to prevent and end violations of human rights, including: violations of mental and physical integrity, freedom of expression and conscience, and freedom from discrimination.

The organization recognizes that governments in different states are the main “recipients” of its work. This does not mean that governments are the main violators of human rights, but the organization's goal is to change the situation in this area through state bodies. Amnesty International's goals include formulating an accurate picture of human rights violations in different countries. One of the organization's weaknesses is that it pays disproportionate attention to developed countries in its reports: lower levels of state control in developed democracies allow for free public dialogue, which in turn leads to acute situations of violence, which in turn leads to new Amnesty International reports and the emergence of similar organizations such as Human Rights Watch.

In April 2024, Amnesty International prepared the State of the World's Human Rights Report, which includes a section on the human rights situation in Ukraine³⁵. This Report, in the context of Ukraine, refers to numerous violations of humanitarian law at the international level, such as indiscriminate shelling, cluster mines and munitions, and prisoners of war. Also, in the report under consideration, Amnesty International noted violations of such human rights as freedom of thought, freedom of belief or religion, violence against girls and women, the rights of the elderly, children's rights, the rights of LGBTIQI people, and the right to a healthy environment³⁶.

A separate structural element of Amnesty International's State of the World's Human Rights Report on Ukraine of April 2024 is a section on the territories occupied by Russia. It addresses human rights violations such as arbitrary deprivation of citizenship, freedom of opinion, arbitrary detention and enforced disappearances, torture and other ill-treatment, the right to unfair trials and education³⁷.

Each of the structural elements of the Report on human rights violations in Ukraine has its own substantive characterization and content.

Here is an example of such a characterization in relation to the right to a fair trial, which is violated by Russia. Persons who were detained in the territories occupied by Russia were held in unrecognized courts for hearings, and the rights of these persons to a fair trial were violated in one way or another. It was a widespread practice to deny the opportunity to choose whom to seek legal assistance, especially in politically motivated

³⁵ The State of the World's Human Rights (2024). <https://www.amnesty.org/en/documents/pol10/7200/2024/en/>

³⁶ The State of the World's Human Rights (2024). *Id.*

³⁷ The State of the World's Human Rights (2024). *Id.*

cases. Families and friends were not informed about their loved ones, so they were forced to spend significant amounts of money on local lawyers to be able to obtain information about detainees and visit places of detention. It was widespread practice that court-appointed lawyers did not act in the best interests of their clients. Inadmissible evidence, such as coerced “confessions”, was taken into account by judges and served as the basis for convictions on charges that were mostly politically motivated³⁸.

Therefore, authors will further highlight the activities of a human rights organization such as Human Rights Watch, which in all parts of the world investigates and reports on abuses occurring. Human Rights Watch is a staff of approximately 550 people of more than 70 nationalities. These people are country lawyers, experts, journalists, and others working to protect the most at-risk populations, from civilians and vulnerable minorities in times of war to children and refugees in need. Human Rights Watch targets armed groups, governments, and businesses to encourage them to change or enforce their policies, laws, and practices.

The main areas of Human Rights Watch's work are shown in Figure 4.

In 2024, Human Rights Watch also prepared Report on the Human Rights Situation in Ukraine. In some respects, it overlaps with the Amnesty International Report and addresses the following issues³⁹:

1. Indiscriminate attacks;
2. Anti-personnel mines and cluster munitions;
3. Crimes during the Russian occupation;
4. Torture and ill-treatment of prisoners of war;
5. Detention of civilians during the armed conflict;
6. Sexual violence during the armed conflict;
7. Attacks on educational institutions; children in boarding schools;
8. The effects of war on the elderly.

³⁸ The State of the World's Human Rights (2024). *Id.*

³⁹ World Report 2024 (2024). <https://www.hrw.org/uk/world-report/2024/country-chapters/ukraine>

Figure 4. The main activities of the Human Rights Watch organization

Source: developed based on Human Rights Watch⁴⁰

The main beneficiaries of the International Federation for Human Rights are its member national human rights organizations and victims of violations of human rights. The International Federation for Human Rights also works with other local partner organizations.

5-DISCUSSION

Wu⁴¹ published a literature review and bibliometric analysis on the human rights discrimination algorithm. Mahdanian et al.⁴² devoted their research to the issue of

⁴⁰ Human Rights Watch (2025). <https://www.hrw.org/about-us>

human rights in mental health care and prepared an overview of the current global situation.

Helm and Nasu⁴³ explored the role and significance of national authorities in relation to various regulatory decisions that have attempted to minimize the negative impact of fake news and related information clutter.

Shany⁴⁴ rightly notes that there is a problem with quality control of new human rights from one particular perspective – reviewing and analyzing the factual justifications provided by standard-setters and legislators seeking to advance the recognition of new human rights through normative instruments (treaties, laws, declarations, etc.).

Authors should also note the work of Dziamulych et al.⁴⁵, which is devoted to the current socio-demographic situation in rural areas of Ukraine.

Comparing the results of this study with the content of other scientific publications, it can be concluded that they differ significantly. For example, there are scholarly works on the algorithm of human rights discrimination, the role and importance of national authorities in various regulatory decisions that have tried to minimize the negative impact of fake news and related information disorder, the problem of quality control of new human rights, and the current socio-demographic situation in rural areas of Ukraine. At the same time, the topic of cooperation between the state and human rights organizations in ensuring human rights has reached a new level thanks to our publication.

CONCLUSION

Thus, authors have comprehensively examined the theoretical aspects of interaction between the state and human rights organizations in ensuring human rights. Authors have characterized the concept of the rule of law and proposed to consider the state of ensuring and observance of human rights as a kind of “indicator” of the rule of

⁴¹ Wu, Y. (2023). Data Governance and Human Rights: An Algorithm Discrimination Literature Review and Bibliometric Analysis. *Journal of Humanities, Arts and Social Science*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.26855/jhass.2023.01.018>

⁴² Mahdanian, A. A., Laporta, M., Drew Bold, N., Funk, M., & Puras, D. (2023). Human rights in mental healthcare; A review of current global situation. *International Review of Psychiatry*, 35(2), 150-162. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09540261.2022.2027348>

⁴³ Helm, R. K., & Nasu, H. (2021). Regulatory responses to ‘fake news’ and freedom of expression: Normative and empirical evaluation. *Human Rights Law Review*, 21(2), 302-328. <https://doi.org/10.1093/hrlr/ngaa060>

⁴⁴ Shany, Y. (2023). The Case for a New Right to a Human Decision Under International Human Rights Law. *SSRN*, 4592244. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4592244>

⁴⁵ Dziamulych, M., Petrukha, S., Yakubiv, V., Zhuk, O., Maiboroda, O., Tesliuk, S., Kolosok, A. (2021). Analysis of the Socio-Demographic State of Rural Areas in the System of their Sustainable Development: a Case Study of Ukraine. *Scientific Papers Series “Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development”*, 21, 4, 223–234. <https://surl.li/wugflp>

law. It is stated that the division of state power into three branches - judicial, executive and legislative - is one of the classic mechanisms for ensuring human rights.

In this research publication, authors also provide arguments for and against the assumption that Ukraine is a state governed by the rule of law through the consideration of such a fundamental human right as the right to a fair trial. A positive argument for this assumption is that Ukraine has a “three-tier” judicial system. The negative argument is the high corruption risks in the work of the courts.

Separately, this study focuses on the control function in the context of interaction between the state and human rights organizations. This aspect is illustrated by the example of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966, which obliges parties to report to the Human Rights Committee on the state of implementation of the Covenant. It is also possible to send observation missions of organizations to the field.

The publication describes the activities of the United Nations as a key actor in international law in the field of human rights. Our study also reflects the activities of the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights. In general, among other human rights organizations, the UN international monitoring mechanism is the most developed.

Authors have also touched upon the human rights activities of such organizations as Amnesty International, Human Rights Watch and the International Federation for Human Rights. Each of them has its own peculiarities in interacting with the state in the context of human rights, which was reflected in the study. In general, the contribution of these human rights organizations to human rights activities can hardly be overestimated.

This paper describes the content of two major reports on the state of human rights observance – the World Human Rights Report prepared by Amnesty International in 2024 and the Human Rights Report on Ukraine in 2024 with the participation of Human Rights Watch.

Further doctrinal research is required on the activities of such human rights organizations as Freedom House, International Commission of Jurists, Front Line Defenders and World Organization Against Torture in the context of their interaction with the governments of the respective states regarding the state of human rights. Without diminishing the importance of the latter human rights organizations, authors would like to emphasize that they have chosen the main ones for this work. However, the activities of Freedom House, the International Commission of Jurists, Front Line Defenders and the World Organization Against Torture may well be the subject of a separate research study.

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